

March 13, 2026

Filipe Alves da Silva
DigiMedia
Universidade de Aveiro
Aveiro, Portuga

Dear Mr. Alves da Silva,

This letter acknowledges that you developed an English to Portuguese translation for the Technology Readiness Index 2.0, originally developed by A. Parasuraman and Charles L. Colby. Professor Parasuraman and I appreciate your work on this document. Per the terms of our agreement, we will share this with other researchers who license the instrument. We expect that you will identify this on your C.V. and will receive professional credit for this excellent work.

Regards,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Charles L. Colby', with a stylized flourish at the end.

Charles L. Colby
Vice President, Senior Advisor and Methodologist
Radius Global Insights
Co-developer of the TRI 2.0